

USING INTERACTIVE METHODS EFFECTIVELY IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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***Annotation:** In this article it is spoken about some effective methods which are highly supposed to use in English classes and expected to ease the way of learning as well as they are considered as a modern way of learning which consists of the interaction of all participants in the educational process: both teacher and students.*

***Key words:** Interactive activities, standard lessons, interactive learning, active interaction, classroom interaction, teacher talk, student talk, classroom management.*

The act of teaching is essentially a constant processing of options. At every point in each lesson, teachers have a number of options available. They can decide to do something meaningful which is also related to their new topic where as not to do anything at all which leads not only their lesson, but also their students to become extremely bored during the whole lesson. In order to become a good teacher, it seems important to be aware of as many options as possible. This may enable them to generate their own rules and guidelines as to what works and what does not work.

Indeed, there is no scientific basis yet for writing such a description of an ideal teaching methodology. Instead, we can observe teachers and learner at work and take note of strategies and approaches that seem to be more beneficial than others, not necessarily in order to copy them, but to become more aware of what is possible. Some teachers still have the same teaching methods which have been used over the years. They may not either want to overwork or spend energy. But they are mistaken

as interactive teaching does not acquire energy, but creativity from the teachers. As the word “interacts” means to have conversation, discussion and debate with each other, in some cases, interactive methods may refer to work as a group or something like that. By using these kinds of styles, teachers may affect the process of the lesson in a good way to become it fascinating. But what can make different and effective their casual lesson? There are some factors that can help them:

First, to start the lesson with warm up questions (which are related to the lesson plan) that often happens in their daily life.

For instance, when a teacher explains about present simple tense, he should ask what they do almost every day. In this case, students may express their ideas by giving examples from their own lives like washing their face, drinking water, sleeping, reading books and actions like that. As we see, although theme is new for them, students are learning it by using their imagination which leads both students and teachers to interact with each other. Then the teacher may follow the next step like how to make sentence with that tense or the other situations that is possible to use.

Second, to create unusual tasks with different ways of explanations. There is a great deal of interactive classroom activities:

- Think-pair-share;
- Role play;
- Ice breaker;
- Jigsaw and etc.

For example, when it comes to talking about the process and advantages of those activities,

- Think-pair-share

This type of activity first asks students to consider a question on their own, and then provides an opportunity for students to discuss it in pairs, and finally together with the whole class. The success of these activities depends on the nature of the questions posed. This activity works ideally with questions to encourage deeper

thinking, problem-solving, and/or critical analysis. The group discussions are critical as they allow students to articulate their thought processes.

The procedure is as follows:

Pose a question, usually by writing it on the board or projecting it.

Have students consider the question on their own (1 – 2 min).

Then allow the students form groups of 2-3 people.

Next, have students discuss the question with their partner and share their ideas and/or contrasting opinions (3 min).

Re-group as a whole class and solicit responses from some or all of the pairs (3 min).

Advantages of the think-pair-share include the engagement of all students in the classroom (particularly the opportunity to give voice to quieter students who might have difficulty sharing in a larger group), quick feedback for the instructor (e.g., the revelation of student misconceptions), encouragement and support for higher levels of thinking of the students.

- Jigsaw

A Jigsaw is a cooperative active learning exercise where students are grouped into teams to solve a problem or analyze a reading. With jigsaw problem solving, students are assigned to groups to solve a complex problem. Each student solves a different part of the problem (making them one piece of the jigsaw puzzle), and then the team comes together to assemble all the pieces and solve the problem (or assemble the puzzle) as a group.

This exercise will give your students both a micro and a macro view of how to solve challenging problems and also brings them together to solve the problem in an interactive way.

Third, to use the demonstration method to give a clear instruction.

That's because, the human-being have been tended to remember facts and events accurately by watching something rather than reading or writing it. It is fact is that to teach action verbs and some words have been difficult over the period of time. But, now it is not concerned as an issue anymore. While teaching action verbs teacher may show the meaning by acting out. For example,

- ✓ To jump (by jumping slightly on the floor)
- ✓ To write (by writing something)
- ✓ To read (by reading a book).

After teaching the meaning and the pronunciation of verbs, teacher may check whether students have understood or not by to do the same actions which have acted out by teacher. For teaching words, instructor writes the word on the board and shows the meaning of that word on the screen. For the first time, teacher should remember along with students, and then he should let them to do on their own.

There are also some kinds of activities which can be done as a game. For example, when a teacher tells his students to write a dictation, it is common situation that they imagine only like that: First, a teacher dictates the text word by word and they will write. But, there are several types of dictation with different ways of dictating:

- Knocking dictation(clapping dictation);
- Picture dictation;
- Running dictation.

The process of the task may be like this:

For “Knocking (clapping)” dictation:

A teacher chooses a simple text which contains approximately 10-15 lines with simple words which are easy to write and understand, and reads out. Then he pauses and either knocks the desk or claps at some parts of the sentences. In this case, students have to guess that which word can be the most suitable to fill the sentence with right meaning. After finishing reading the whole text, the teacher will read the text with correct answers. Then, they may be aware of their scores. The purpose of

this task is to improve students' skills to guess accurately. At least, the feature of the text may be like this:

My house

"I live in a house with my family. My _____(1) is big. It has a garage, hall, bathroom, kitchen, living room and three bedrooms. There is a _____(2) in our garage. We have breakfast, dinner and _____(3) in our dining room. I love my house.

For "Picture dictation":

The teacher describes a picture, or sequence of pictures, to students who draw what they hear. The aim is for close listening, the drawing should be quick and simple. Normally the exercise takes about 20–30 minutes, depending on the length of the dictation. Using this activity is highly supposed to increase learners' imagination and remember the details wisely.

For "Running dictation":

In this task, students are divided into teams and complete a relay race—one member RUNS to a specific location to read information, then RUNS back to the team to report it, where a secretary transcribes it.

A running dictation is typically used to review the events of a story, but it is extremely versatile and can truly be used with anything: definitions, descriptions, facts...you name it! There are many different roles that you can add and ways to extend the activity, and I encourage you to try all of them. As you read through these instructions, consider how you might adapt it to best suit your purposes! As it is mentioned above, it is a review activity. Traditionally, language teachers have used this fast-paced team game to review a story. Students benefit from repeated exposure to information and to language, and so content area teachers will find this activity just as helpful as language teachers.

Finally, to use songs during the lesson. It does not mean that teacher may use any kind of musing, but to use songs and music which contains the topic based information. Note, every task and step should be based on the concrete and

reasonable purpose. Using that method has been proved as one of the best ways of revising knowledge.

To conclude, interactive teaching strategies can be a powerful tool for promoting engagement, critical thinking, and deeper learning. By incorporating these strategies into your classroom, you can create a dynamic and stimulating learning environment that fosters a love of learning. This keeps them more interested and engaged, makes it impossible for them to just sit and zone out, and helps them learn and integrate the information better.

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